

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION OF SCARF JOINTS WITH MISMATCHED ADHERENDS

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Keywords: *Damage tolerance, dissimilar material systems, quasi-static tensile, adhesively bonded*

1 Introduction

Repairs to composite structures require the removal of the damaged material, followed by an adhesively bonded scarf repair. Scarf repairs are designed to maintain a flush surface profile. This is particularly important for aerodynamic surfaces or regions with moving mechanical parts. The scarf patch is commonly identical, in terms of ply thickness, orientation and material, to the original structure [1]. However, aircraft manufacturers are faced with the task of choosing a different repair material because either the parent materials are no longer available or not certified for field repair applications. In this context, the use of materials different from the parent structures in both ply thickness and mechanical properties presents new challenges, such as mismatch in local and global stiffness. Thus, it is important to address this new problem of scarf repairs with mismatched adherends.

The Federal Aviation Regulation (FAR) states that bonded repairs need to firstly withstand the design ultimate load with damage up to a detectable threshold [2] and maintain continued safe flight with the complete disbond of the repairs. This requirement is based on damage tolerance principles and must be met by either demonstrating residual strength experimentally or by analyses, under various loading conditions [3-5]. Therefore it is important to develop validated methodologies that can accurately predict the effects of disbonds on the load-carrying capacities of adhesively bonded scarf joints and repairs.

The design and prediction of the strength in adhesively bonded repairs are traditionally based on the assumption that failure is cohesive, i.e., the crack propagation is entirely within the adhesive [6]. From a fracture mechanics viewpoint, the occurrence of fracture in a material corresponds to when the strain

energy release rate (SERR) reaches a critical value. However, most structural adhesives are engineered to possess fracture toughness higher than the interlaminar fracture toughness of composite laminates, raising the possibility of failure being within the composite adherend [7].

In this paper, we present an experimental investigation and computational modelling of the disbond tolerance behaviour of scarf joints between mismatched material systems. The fracture paths and modes of failure in mismatched adherends were examined using microscopy techniques. The results of a comparison study between the experimental results and computational modelling revealed that a linear elastic fracture mechanics model with composite properties is able to predict the load-carrying strength of mismatched composite adherends.

2 Methodology

Scarf joints are two-dimensional representations of scarf repairs along the most highly loaded direction. Scarf joint specimens were designed to achieve identical thickness as the original structure, to represent scarf repairs that are designed to maintain a flush profile with the structure. Both joint adherends were manufactured from two different woven carbon/epoxy prepreg composite material systems: Cycom970/T300 (Cycom970) and HexPly914/T300 (HexPly914). Both systems differ in mechanical properties, fracture strengths and ply thicknesses. The HexPly914 and the Cycom970 have a curing temperature of 180°C under vacuum for two hours. VTA260 structural adhesive was used to bond the adherends at a curing temperature of 120°C under vacuum for one hour. Tables 1-3 summarise the material properties and ply thicknesses.

Two sets of composite scarf joints were manufactured. In the first set of joints the Cycom970 was used for the parent adherend, with HexPly914 being the repair adherend; in the second set of joints the materials for the parent and repair adherends were swapped. The parent adherend was a $[0/45]_{2S}$ laminate that was cured first. Upon curing the total adherend thickness was 2.64 mm for the HexPly914 and 1.76 mm for the Cycom970. Each adherend was cut to a width of 25.4 mm and a length of 150 mm. The parent adherends were machined at a 3-degree angle to represent typical aircraft repairs. For the repair adherends, the layup was varied to match the thickness of the parent adherend. The Cycom970 repair used a $[0_2/45_2/0/45]_S$ ply sequence and the HexPly914 repair used a $[0/45/0/45/0]$ ply sequence. The repair adherend plies were laid in an inverse stepped configuration using the scarfed parent adherend as mould. It is noteworthy to mention that this manufacturing method creates small resin rich pocket at the ply ends along the scarf. The resulting scarf joint as described above is shown in Fig. 1.

Before curing the repair adherend, a layer of 5 μm thick non-stick polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) film was laid between the repair and parent adherends. This ensured that the adherends remained separate during the cure. The cured adherends were assembled together with an adhesive. PTFE films of three different lengths (3, 6 and 12 mm) were embedded at the feathered end of the repair adherend to simulate disbond between the adhesive and the repair adherend. This disbond replicated damage on the repair due to manufacturing or accidental impact damage during service, to create a joint containing disbond. Joints without disbond, or "pristine" joints, were also manufactured as benchmark specimens. At least four samples of each disbond length were manufactured. The assembled joints were cured in autoclave in accordance with the manufacturer's recommended curing process.

The pristine and embedded disbond joints were tested to determine the influence of mismatched adherends on the residual strength of scarf joints with disbonds. The joints were loaded at both ends in quasi-static tension using a 50 kN Instron machine at a constant displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min until the joints broke apart. The load required to fracture the joint was recorded during the entire process. The test provided the strength of the bonded mismatched adherends with interfacial

disbonds. The opposing fracture surfaces were placed under a scanning electron microscope (SEM) to determine the fracture behaviour and the crack propagation path through the thickness of the joint. This was used to guide the development of the computational models and to provide insights towards improving the scarf joint design for better damage tolerant properties.

3 Experimental results

3.1 Residual strength of mismatched scarf adherends

The average strengths of the joints at varying disbond lengths were plotted against the size of the disbond a , normalised by the scarf length L , as shown in Fig. 2. All joints were observed to have fractured catastrophically. The ply orientation along the plane of the scarf is added in the figure. It was observed that the strength of the scarf was fairly similar for small disbond lengths (less than 3 mm). As disbond size increased, the strength of the joint reduced dramatically in a non-linear rate. For the same disbond size, the strength of the joint was similar for both HexPly914 and Cycom970 parent adherend configurations.

The strength of a joint is determined by the strength of the load-carrying plies, so that the loss of these plies as a result of the disbond results in a significant loss of strength in the joint. Furthermore, a disbond that places the crack tip at a ply with low elasticity reduces the fracture toughness of the joint. By matching the strength of the joint at a given disbond length against the superimposed ply orientation as shown in Fig. 2, it was discovered that the loss in strength for a 3 mm to 6 mm disbond length coincided with the loss of 0° plies.

3.2 Fracture behaviour of joints

In scarf joints with disbonds lengths of 6 mm and 12 mm, examination using optical microscope initially suggested a cohesive failure close to the composite-adhesive interface. However, detailed analysis using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) revealed the presence of carbon fibres on both fracture surfaces as shown in Fig. 3. On the repair adherend at the crack tip, the fracture surface showed presence of adhesive carrier material on the composite fracture surface. The opposite surface showed no adhesive,

indicating a predominant composite fracture. The same observation was true for the entire fracture surface. It is, therefore, concluded that the fracture path was neither at the composite-adhesive interface nor in the adhesive, but inside the composite adherend.

The mismatched adherent joints were inspected to understand the effect of different mechanical properties on the fracture propagation as shown in Fig. 4. Fractographic analysis showed that for relatively small disbond sizes, less than 3 mm, the adherends failed due to net tension failure across the laminate. This behaviour suggested that the adhesive bondline, mainly loaded in shear, had a higher strength than the tensile strength of the composite adherends. The fact that failure of both type of joints (with disbond less than 3 mm) failed by net tension fracture of HexPly914 laminate is consistent with the fact this laminate has lower in-plane strength than the Cycom970 laminate. For scarf joints and scarf repairs to recover the design strength of the structure, fracture in the repair adherend is undesirable. So it is important to consider laminate strengths for mismatched repairs to select repair materials with higher strength than the parent structure, if the tolerable disbonds are small (less than 3 mm in the present case).

For larger disbond sizes, the fracture propagated across the adhesive into the parent adherend. This was followed by bondline composite fracture and net tension failure at the other feathered end of the scarf adherend. This behaviour was fairly similar to the fracture path of matched ply joints [7]. This suggests that the failure was not related to the ply property and the lay-up of the adherends, but can be attributed to geometrical factors such as secondary bending. This behaviour requires further study to determine the mode of fracture at the crack tip and the change in adherend stiffness with respect to changes in disbond length.

4 Numerical validation of experimental findings

4.1 Methodology

For a scarf joint, it is known that fracture occurring in an adherend is attributed to the strength of the adherend material [8]. However, fracture occurring in the bondline due to adhesive disbond is relatively unknown. A numerical methodology was developed

to predict the strength of the joints with fracture along the bondline. Based on experimental findings on the fracture path and behaviour, finite element models were developed in Abaqus 6.10 [9]. Plane strain elements were used to model the adhesive and the composite adherends at the ply level, as a stack of individual plies rather a laminate. Material properties were applied based on values from Table 1 and Table 2 for the composite plies and adhesive respectively. The fracture properties for the composite materials in Mode I and II delamination are shown in Table 3. Material properties were obtained experimentally and from manufacturer’s data. Fracture properties were obtained by performing mode I and II tests. Boundary conditions were applied on both ends of the scarf joint to replicate experimental testing constraints, and consisted of constrained displacements in all degrees of freedom, except for the loading displacement at one end. A non-linear implicit numerical analysis was performed using Abaqus/Standard.

Table 1. Material properties of composite plies

	Cycom 970/T300	HexPly 914/T300
E11 = E22 (GPa)	53.1	53.7
E33 (GPa)	3.00	3.90
$\nu_{13} = \nu_{23}$	0.20	0.20
ν_{12}	0.08	0.08
G13 = G23 (GPa)	0.79	0.67
G12 (GPa)	0.88	0.50
Ply thickness (mm)	0.22	0.33

Table 2. Material properties of VTA260 adhesive

<i>E</i>	ν	<i>G</i>
3.0 GPa	0.35	1.1 GPa

Table 3. Fracture properties of the composite materials

	Cycom 970/T300	HexPly 914/T300
G_{Ic} (KJ/m ²)	0.329	0.256
G_{IIc} (KJ/m ²)	2.565	1.290

Based on the fractographic observations described in the previous section that fracture occurred in the composite at a small distance, comparable to the fibre diameter, away from the composite-adhesive interface, the onset and propagation of cracks were assumed to take place along the composite-adhesive interface. Since the thin layer of resin-fibre material removed from the composite adherend was extremely small, its effect is not considered in this investigation. The virtual crack closure technique (VCCT) was used to model damage propagation.

The VCCT is a well-established numerical technique to calculate the strain energy release rate at a crack tip. It is a linear elastic fracture mechanics analysis based on the product of the nodal forces, F , at the crack tip and nodal displacements, v , immediately behind the crack tip. Assuming the width and length of element are b and d , respectively, the strain energy release rate (SERR), G is given by the following expression,

$$G = \frac{F v}{2 b d} \quad (1)$$

Disbond at the crack tip occurs when G approaches the critical value, G_c , ie.

$$\frac{G}{G_c} \geq 1 \quad (2)$$

In a mixed mode loading condition, the critical SERR was defined by the Benzeggagh-Kenane (B-K) fracture criterion [10], which is given by

$$G_c = G_{Ic} + (G_{IIc} - G_{Ic}) \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_I + G_{II}} \right)^\eta \quad (3)$$

where the exponent, η , is an empirical parameter. It was found that brittle, epoxy based composite materials correlated well with an exponent value of 1.75 [11] and was used for both composite materials in this paper.

Within Abaqus, the VCCT is incorporated into a progressive damage model that allows for automated modelling of crack propagation in a non-linear analysis. In this model, a damageable interface is defined as a bonded contact between two surfaces. A pre-existing disbonded region is defined, which

involves only a touching contact (free to open but cannot interpenetrate), and this is used to automatically define the crack tip. At the end of every increment in a non-linear analysis, Equation (2) is assessed at a crack tip node. If crack growth is deemed to occur, then the bonded contact at that node is converted to a touching contact for the next increment. In this way, automated crack progression can be captured, allowing for the simulation of stable crack growth, or crack growth occurring in a non-catastrophic manner. In this paper, the term “VCCT model” is used to refer to the Abaqus crack growth methodology incorporating the VCCT Equation (1).

4.2 Strength prediction

Models corresponding to embedded disbond lengths of 3, 4, 6, 9, 12 mm were generated. Two VCCT models were employed to predict the strength of the scarf joints, as shown in Fig. 5. The first numerical model, Model A, replicates experimentally embedded disbonds at the repair-adhesive interface. The VCCT model, assigned with repair properties, was embedded for the remaining length of the repair-adhesive interface to represent a bonded contact. In the second numerical model, Model B, the disbond was located at the parent-adhesive interface, thus, allowed the VCCT model to be embedded along the parent-adhesive interface and the VCCT model was assigned with parent properties. The numerical model of the scarf joint was loaded in tension by increasing end displacement until the joint completely failed.

Numerical results from Model A and B provided much insight on the fracture behaviour of mismatched scarf joints. In this paper, the terms “Cycom970 joint” and “HexPly914 joint” is, respectively, used to refer to joints with Cycom 970 and HexPly914 as the parent adherend. It was observed that Model A predicted the strength of Cycom970 joints well but overpredicted the strength of HexPly914 joints. This is due to the difference in SERR between Cycom970 and HexPly914 composite plies, as shown in Table 3. Furthermore, Model A does not represent experimental observations of its fracture mode. The fracture mode in both joint designs belonged to the parent adherend, as illustrated in Fig. 4. Results from Model B showed that for disbond sizes greater than 6 mm, the model was fairly capable of predicting the

strength of the joint. However, at disbond sizes of less than 6 mm, the results failed to converge with experimental findings. Between the two designs, Model B showed consistency in correlating with experimental values, suggesting that Model B has captured the fracture mode of the joint. However, Model B has failed to capture the fracture path as described in Fig. 4, leading to an overprediction of the joint strength with decreasing disbond size. For a better comparison of joint strengths, values are shown in Table 4.

Results shown in this section suggest that accurate simulation of the fracture mode and path is capable of accurately predicting the strength of mismatched joints. Further work will be required to introduce higher fidelity simulations that will accurately predict the strength of mismatched joints.

Table 4. Scarf joint strength

HexPly914 Parent			
a (mm)	Model A (MPa)	Model B (MPa)	Experimental (MPa)
3	432	1125	306
4	397	520	-
6	337	244	227
9	250	197	-
12	214	169	154
Cycom970 Parent			
a (mm)	Model A (MPa)	Model B (MPa)	Experimental (MPa)
3	317	1348	310
4	288	1016	-
6	213	298	237
9	168	199	-
12	158	164	174

5 Conclusion

The fracture behaviour of composite scarf joints containing a disbond between un-matched adherends has been investigated through tensile tests and computational modelling. The experimental results reveal that at short disbond lengths, less than 3 mm in the present case, scarf joints failed by net tension failure of the weaker adherend. When disbonds were longer than 3 mm, fracture occurred by delamination of the

parent adherend, at a very small distance, comparable to fibre diameter, adjacent to the adhesive layer.

A numerical analysis was performed to determine the factors required to accurately predict the strength of the mismatched scarf joints using a VCCT-based model. Furthermore, numerical analysis confirmed with fractographic observations that the fracture occurred in the composite adherend; not in the adhesive.

References

- [1] FAA, FAA Federal Aviation Regulations (FAR) Part 23, Section 573-Damage tolerance and fatigue evaluation of structure, 2005.
- [2] Sela N., Ishai O., Interlaminar fracture toughness and toughening of laminated composite materials: a review, *Composites*, 20 (1989) 423-35.
- [3] Harman A.B., Wang C.H., Damage tolerance and impact resistance of composite scarf joints, ICCM-16, Kyoto, Japan, 2007.
- [4] Kim M.K., Elder D.J., Wang C.H., Feih S., Interaction of laminate damage and adhesive disbonding in composite scarf joints subjected to combined in-plane loading and impact, *Composite Structures*, 94 (2012) 945-53.
- [5] Wang C.H., Gunnion A.J., Orifici A.C., Rider A., Residual strength of composite laminates containing scarfed and straight-sided holes, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 42 (2011) 1951-61.
- [6] Hart-Smith L., McDonnell-Douglas Corp. L.B., CA, Adhesive-bonded scarf and stepped-lap joints, McDonnell-Douglas Corp., Long Beach, CA, 1973.
- [7] Wang C., Goh J., Ahamed J., Glynn A., Georgiadis S., Damage Tolerance Analysis of Adhesively Bonded Repairs to Composite Structures, Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Composite Materials. Jeju, South Korea, 2011.
- [8] Wang C.H., Gunnion A.J., On the design methodology of scarf repairs to composite laminates, *Composites Science and Technology*, 68 (2008) 35-46.
- [9] Abaqus Version 6.10 Documentation, Abaqus Inc., Rhode Island, USA, 2009.
- [10] Benzeggagh M.L., Kenane M., Measurement of mixed-mode delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites with mixed-mode bending apparatus, *Composites Science and Technology*, 56 (1996) 439-49.
- [11] Camanho P.P., Davila C.G., de Moura M.F., Numerical Simulation of Mixed-Mode Progressive Delamination in Composite Materials, *Journal of Composite Materials*, 37 (2003) 1415-38.

Fig. 1. Manufacturing schematic of a scarf joint with mismatched adherends

Fig. 2. Residual strength of mismatched adherend scarf joints with disbonds superimposed with its respective ply orientations along the plane of the scarf. The data points represent disbond lengths of 0 mm, 3 mm, 6 mm and 12 mm.

Fig. 3. Typical bondline composite fracture in the joint observed under the SEM.

Fig. 4. Observed crack propagation along the bondline of scarf joints with varying disbond lengths.

Fig. 5. Schematic of two modelling methodologies used to determine the strength of the scarf. Model A: Disbond embedded at the repair-adhesive interface. VCCT model assigned with composite properties of the repair adherend. Model B: Disbond located at the parent-adhesive interface. VCCT model assigned with composite properties of the parent adherend.

Fig. 6. Numerical prediction of scarf joints with Cycom970 parent adherend

Fig. 7. Numerical prediction of scarf joints with HexPly914 parent adherend